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NLRP2 is silenced during human papillomavirus infection.

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We found by studying total transcription in two infection settings, in HPV16 infection of the human foreskin and in transduction of primary keratinocytes with HPV16 genome that the NLR family gene NLRP2 was silenced following HPV infection. DNA tumor virus infection was associated with strong silencing of an NLR.